

MAIN ACTIVITIES

Creating **teaching materials** for university classes on heritage outreach and community involvement to promote diversity in heritage education

Development of **new technological features** for the ArchaeoTrail system, providing a pluri-vocal dissemination of heritage narratives

Enabling **diverse perspectives** in smartphone heritage tours

Creation of **smartphone tours** in the Czech Republic, Serbia and Spain in cooperation with different local actors: communities, students, archaeologists

Development of **guidelines and video tutorials** for local communities to independently create smartphone tours using the ArchaeoTrail system

Evaluation and **dissemination of all materials** (guidelines, teaching materials, trails) with different audiences (local communities, students, etc.)

Raising awareness of cultural diversity and empowering rural communities

SHARITAGE

Digitally enabled
**community-based European
SHARed cultural herITAGE
engagement**

SHARITAGE

...aims to promote diversity and inclusion in university heritage education by developing innovative digital tools that enable communities to actively engage with their own heritage. The project aims to bring community voices and perspectives to the forefront of university teaching and learning.

Building on the **ArchaeoTrail system** – an open platform for creating smartphone-based heritage tours – SHARITAGE will add technical features that enhance accessibility, and will create comprehensive guidelines and adaptable teaching resources. This will support the integration of the ArchaeoTrail system into heritage curricula across Europe, encouraging more participatory and inclusive approaches to cultural education.

ArchaeoTrail System

The ArchaeoTrail system consists of a **web portal and a smartphone app**. The web portal allows archaeologists and others to create interactive trails featuring geo-referenced stations with text, images, audio, video, and quizzes about archaeological sites. The accompanying app enables visitors to explore these trails through self-guided tours – all completely free of charge.

CONSORTIUM

The consortium contains **ten** partners from **six** different European countries:

University of Würzburg (GER)
Project Coordinator

Autentek Development (GER)

Charles University Prague (CZE)

Constantine the Philosopher
University in Nitra (SVK)

Goethe University Frankfurt am Main (GER)

Institute of Heritage Sciences
(INCIPIT-CSIC) (ESP)

Institute for the Protection of
Cultural Monuments of Serbia (SRB)

University of Belgrade (SRB)

University of South Bohemia (CZE)

University of Wrocław (POL)

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archaeotrail.org/sharitage [Sharitage](https://www.facebook.com/Sharitage)

ERASMUS+ COOPERATION PARTNERSHIPS 2025-1-DE01-KA220-HED-000351808

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